

From individual to joint species distribution models: a comparison of model complexity and predictive performance

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Significant Responses in the Hierarchical Multi-Species Model

In the hierarchical multi-species model UF0, statistically significant positive and negative responses for all taxa were identified at a 5% level based on the respective 5th and 95th quantiles of the marginal posterior taxon-specific parameter distributions (β_{kj}^{taxa}). The following plot shows significant positive (1), significant negative (-1), and non-significant responses (0) visualized for all taxa. Taxa are ordered by decreasing number of occurrences. Note that as taxa decrease in the number of occurrences, significant responses become less frequent.

